

Critical Bleeding in Duodenal GIST: A Case Report

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Introduction

Gastrointestinal stromal tumors (GISTs) are rare mesenchymal neoplasms of the digestive tract, most commonly located in the stomach and small intestine, while duodenal involvement is uncommon. Although often asymptomatic, GISTs may present with life-threatening complications, such as acute gastrointestinal hemorrhage, due to their rich vascularization.

Case Presentation

A 60-year-old woman presented to the emergency department in hypovolemic shock, with hypotension, tachycardia, and melena with fresh blood clots. Preoperatively, upper gastrointestinal endoscopy revealed an ulcerated tumor with active bleeding, without the possibility of achieving endoscopic hemostasis. The patient was subsequently referred for imaging, and computed tomography identified a retroperitoneal mass invading the duodenum. The scan demonstrated an invasive tumor at the level of the second portion of the duodenum (D2), with active intratumoral hemorrhage and intraluminal contrast extravasation. Additionally, multiple vascular connections were observed between the tumor and the inferior vena cava, as well as involvement of the superior mesenteric vessels. Intraoperatively, a large, highly vascularized gastrointestinal stromal tumor was identified, located anterior to the inferior vena cava and to the right of the superior mesenteric pedicle, with multiple adhesions to the surrounding vascular structures. As an emergency, a cephalic duodenopancreatectomy was performed, followed by hepaticojejunal, pancreaticogastroic, and precolic gastrojejunal anastomoses. The postoperative course was uneventful, and the patient was discharged on postoperative day 7. At 6-month follow-up, no tumor recurrence was observed.

Conclusion

The particularities of this case consist in the absence of complications in an elderly patient with a life-threatening hemorrhage from a duodenal gastrointestinal stromal tumor and in the complex surgical approach.

Keywords

hypovolemic shock, cephalic duodenopancreatectomy, retroperitoneal tumour